

Village Community Resilience in Handling the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Resilient city is a concept that emerged as an effort to overcome natural disasters that often occur in urban areas. Disaster management based on local wisdom is an effective strategy to encourage community enthusiasm to prevent and manage the impact of disasters. Disaster management strategies based on local wisdom as social capital can be implemented by strengthening community resilience. The increasing escalation of the impact of the non-natural disaster Covid-19 has made all people, regions, and countries take countermeasures independently and collectively. The smallest group of society is also required to have high adaptability and resilience. The Resilient Village social movement that has been implemented in the Malang Regency area is studied as an effort to contain the Covid-19 pandemic. The purpose of this study was to determine the response of the community regarding the seven (7) elements of resilience determined in the resilient village social movement. Respondents' perceptions of the resilient village social movement were examined through several indicators for each resilience element. The resilience of human resources is measured by the level of confidence in the existence of Covid-19, the willingness to be a cadre for disaster management and the urgency of a resilient village. Food Resilience is assessed based on the increase in food demand, food availability and food resilience urgency. Health Resilience is researched based on the efforts of healthy resilient families, resilient health cadres and the urgency of healthy health. The resilience of security and order was examined in the improvement of security and order, the role of security and order officers and the need for strong security and order. Information resilience is assessed based on the increased need for information, information delivery and the need for robust information during the Covid-19 pandemic. Psychological resilience is researched according to the improvement of family psychology, the need for psychological cadres and the need for psychological strength. Cultural resilience is studied based on a culture of sharing, a culture of reminding others, a culture of helping, a culture of tolerance and the need for cultural resilience.

Introduction

Countries joined in the United Nations (United Nations) took the initiative to seek disaster management concepts that can be applied to various types of natural and non-natural disasters [1]. Resilient city is a concept that emerged as an effort to overcome natural disasters that often occur in urban areas [2]. The concept of resilient (resilience) is defined as a system that is more resilient to disasters, accelerates the process of bouncing back, mitigating and recovering from disasters [3]. Basically, this resilience concept rests on the development of systems and the capacity of an area to adapt to the arrival and occurrence of disasters [4].

Village communities have their own local wisdom in dealing with situations that occur in their area. In Javanese terms, *deso mowo coro* which means every village has its own way [5]. The treasures found in each village are often interpreted as local wisdom [6]. Disaster management based on local wisdom is an effective strategy to encourage community enthusiasm to prevent and manage the impact of disasters [7]. Approaches based on local wisdom include community / village / sub-district based disaster management activities [8].

Disaster management strategies based on local wisdom as social capital can be done by strengthening community resilience [9]. Law Number 24 of 2007 concerning Disaster Management mandates protecting communities from the threat of disasters [10]. One of the strategies to achieve this is through developing resilient villages / sub-district against disasters with community-based disaster risk reduction (PRBBK). In CBDRM, the disaster risk management process actively involves the community in assessing, analyzing, managing, monitoring and evaluating disaster risk to reduce vulnerability and improve its capacity [11].

As a result of the socio-economic changes of rural communities after the Covid-19 pandemic, it is possible to lead to drastic socio-economic changes in rural communities [12]. The impact of socio-economic changes in

rural communities during the Covid-19 pandemic was influenced by background demographic characteristics such as age, education, occupation and gender. The PSBB policy and the implementation of health protocols bring about changes and socio-economic impacts on the community [13].

Resilient Village (KpT) is a form of social movement with the principle of mutual cooperation. The social movement which was initiated by Brawijaya University with stakeholder synergy chose the scope of a village equivalent to Citizens Association, or hamlet (outside Java), sub-hamlet (Java). The resilient village adopts the android system method where all software (resilience) can be installed and easily upgraded. The resilient village will also always be updated because it adapts to local conditions [14].

The Resilient Village social movement that has been implemented in the Malang Regency area is studied as an effort to contain the Covid-19 pandemic. The purpose of this study was to determine the response of the community regarding the seven (7) elements of resilience determined in the resilient village social movement. A resilient village social movement as an alternative, simple and applicable solution to tackling the Covid-19 pandemic, whose end time is not yet certain.

Literature

Covid-19 Non-Natural National Disaster

On April 13, 2020, the President of Indonesia, Joko Widodo declared Covid-19 a National Disaster with Presidential Decree (Kepres) Number 12 of 2020 [15]. The spread of Covid-19 has had an impact on increasing the number of victims and property losses, expanding the coverage of areas affected by disasters, and having implications for broad socio-economic aspects in Indonesia [16]. The community is the first to face the risk of a non-natural national disaster Covid-19, so they must be able to deal with it.

The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic around the world shows the potential for social conflict, especially in countries that cannot respond to this situation appropriately. These countries experienced shocks in their social systems, mostly as a result of economic shocks due to the implementation of quarantine and social distancing policies [17]. The impacts arising from the non-natural Covid-19 disaster need to be handled in a planned, integrated, coordinated and comprehensive manner. Disaster management planning can be prepared at the community / community level. This is an effort to accelerate capacity building at the community level to manage and reduce disaster risk [18].

Disaster Management

The increasing escalation of the impact of the non-natural disaster Covid-19 has made all people, regions, and countries take countermeasures independently and collectively. The smallest group of society is also required to have high adaptability and resilience [19]. The uncertainty over the end of the Covid-19 pandemic demands that people take systemic, massive, and effective countermeasures [20]. The PSBB policy, the transition period, to make peace with Covid-19 and the new normal needs to get the support of social movements at the grassroots level, because these policies are still macro in nature and multi interpretations [21].

Disaster management planning is very much needed as a preparedness step in facing the possibility of a disaster / emergency that reaches down to the smallest community of the community. More systematic countermeasures rely entirely on the strength of mutual cooperation and local wisdom of the community, so that the task force that has been formed at the lowest level of the village / sub-district to the village / Citizens Association / community level is easy to apply [22].

In Indonesia, disaster management is regulated in Law Number 24 of 2007. Disaster management consists of 3 (three) stages covering pre-disaster, during emergency response; and post-disaster [10]. In technical implementation, the three stages are often described in the disaster management cycle which consists of prevention and mitigation, preparedness, response and disaster impact [23].

Resilience

An area can be said to be resilient (tough) when it is connected and synergized between the three supporting elements of resilience. So, it can be said that the more resilient a region is, the more it has good innovation, adaptation and mitigation in disaster management [24]. The supporting elements of resilience are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Elements of resilience in an area

The vast territory of the Republic of Indonesia is impossible for the Government to be able to cope with the non-natural national disaster of Covid-19 itself. Community empowerment which is carried out by increasing the capacity of the community in disaster-prone areas is needed so that people can face high risks and are resilient to various disasters [25].

Resilient Village

The concept of Resilient Village which was compiled by the academic community of Universitas Brawijaya in which the author participated in it was made as an alternative reference for the prevention of Covid-19 at the community / Village / Citizens Association level. Resilient Village is a social movement at the community / village / Citizens Association level to cope with disasters [14]. The urgency of the existence of Resilient Village is explained in Figure 2. below.

Figure 2. Urgency of Resilient Village (KpT)

Based on Figure 2., a resilient village is an effort to strengthen action against Covid 19 that is easily carried out independently by the community. The implications of a resilient village social movement can be felt more quickly in the response to Covid-19, if it gets support from central to regional governments and officials at the field level. The translation of various policies is very important so that the movement becomes more directed, efficient, effective, and measured, not only in terms of material but also personnel and time [14].

The concept of a resilient village, which was initiated by the academic community of Universitas Brawijaya, focuses on the installation of the community / village / Citizens Association component in the non-natural disaster management for Covid-19. The resilient village social movement as mentioned in the Guidebook has been compiled in a simple way, so that the Citizens Association, Viillage Guidance Officer, Bhayangkara Fostering Public Security and Order, and lowest government officials can become initiators without going through special assistance. This was done because the spread of Covid-19 was very fast, so all countermeasures must also be quickly replicated throughout Indonesia [14].

Method

Research Design

The research design that will be taken is needed to determine the technical research framework. In this study, researchers used a qualitative research method with a case study approach of the village social movement tough starting with field observations, filling out questionnaires and interviews related to in-depth research objectives

with key informants. In this qualitative study, researchers explored field data about the resilience of rural communities during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In addition to observations and interviews, researchers also carried out field documentation activities, either in the form of images or audio visuals. Furthermore, from all the data obtained, the researcher processed and analyzed the data, and provided the meaning of the discussion described in a narrative. The research hope in the discussion is to focus on the depth and detail of the interviews with key informants, namely cadres of the resilient village social movements.

Location and Time

The research location was carried out on 20 respondents who lived in Kalisongo Village and Sitirejo Village, Malang Regency. The location of this research was chosen based on various considerations, including that the area has established itself as a resilient village with optimal support from various stakeholders and there has been no research that examines the resilience of the community in the non-natural disaster management of Covid-19. This research was carried out based on a schedule that had been planned for 6 months, from February 2020 to July 2020.

Data Analysis Methods

In this qualitative research, the researcher examined all data collected from various sources in Kalisongo Village and Sitirejo Village, Malang Regency including: interviews with key informants, observations in the form of field notes, pictures or photos and videos. In the process of qualitative data analysis, there are three important components, namely: data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions.

After the data is collected from the field, it is then processed first (data editing and conversion) so that the data that is widely distributed in the questionnaire items can be made more concise and simpler. Furthermore, the analysis is carried out so that the raw data obtained from the field has meaning and meaning so that it can answer the problems posed.

Result

Basically, KpT uses the working principle of the Android system where the more resilience or Apps are installed, the more resilient the system that works in it. The increasing number of apps in the Android system shows that more and more people depend on the KpT system that has been installed in the community elements of a community / village / Citizens Association. The Kpt social movement consists of elements of defense and social order enforcement as a security approach, and social service functions are under the authority of the government.

Installing a resilient village does not mean building a new social structure, starting from planning to implementation. However, installing resilient village elements was sufficient by restructuring the existing system in the village / community / Citizens Association. After restructuring the elements of society according to the needs of the resilience element, upgrading human resources is needed to make them compatible with competencies and capacities. Enough assistance personnel Vilage Guidance Officer, Bhayangkara Fostering Public Security and Order, sub-district employees, and Citizens Association independently can build a Resilient village in their neighborhood. The results of the study of the resilience element by the researcher are presented in the following sub-chapters.

Resilience of Human Resource

Human Resource Resilience (HR) is at the center of all elements of resilience in KpT. The organizational structure is made as simple as possible by considering the responsibilities, capacities and availability of human resources in carrying out the functions and tasks of resilience. The organizational structure in a resilient village is certainly not rigid and can be adapted to the conditions of the local village / community / Citizens Association. Data on respondents' perceptions of the belief in a non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 1. as follows.

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2020

Figure 3. Respondents' beliefs about Covid-19

In Figure 3., respondents stated that they were very confident about the occurrence of a non-natural national disaster Covid-19 with a percentage of 95%. A small proportion of respondents said they were unsure about the

occurrence of a non-natural national disaster Covid-19 with a percentage of 5%. In the early days of the Covid-19 pandemic, rural communities did not really know about non-natural disasters and the type of virus that was becoming an epidemic. Over time, the news and the speed of information that spread to remote villages gave rise to the belief that a non-natural disaster Covid-19 was happening..

Based on the following Figure 4., 85% of respondents stated that they were willing to unconditionally / voluntarily be part of the non-natural disaster management for Covid-19. The rest, respondents are willing to take a role in KpT with a condition of 15%. KpT is composed of cross-disciplines and professions ranging from experts in social engineering, economics, food security, political science, to artists and cultural observers. The preparation of SOPs in the KpT was also supervised by elements of the TNI and Polri in terms of defense, security and order. Data on respondents' perceptions of willingness to take a role in overcoming the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 2. as follows.

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2020

Figure 4. Willingness to be a resilient village cadre

Data on respondents' perceptions of the urgency of the Resilient Village movement in overcoming the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 3..

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2020

Figure 5. Urgency of Resilient Village

In Figure 5., 75% of respondents said that the KpT social movement was very much needed in overcoming the non-natural national disaster of Covid-19. Meanwhile, 25% of respondents stated the need for a KpT social movement as an effort to tackle the non-natural national disaster Covid-19.

Food Resilience

PKK cadres and dasa wisma, for example, can have their skills added in managing food barns so that they support the installation of village food barns (LPK). Installing LPK in KpT is needed to increase the food resilience of residents and is not dependent on government assistance. KpT cadres can make LPK and initiate donations of basic necessities for underprivileged residents.

LPK activities are recorded neatly in the form of donors and recipients of basic necessities. During the PSBB and afterwards, efforts were made for the underprivileged to continue to obtain basic food needs. Data on respondents' perceptions of the increase in family food needs during Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 6. Increasing food demand

In Figure 6., respondents with a percentage of 50% stated that there was a slight increase in food needs during the Covid-19 pandemic and 20% stated that there was no increase in family food needs. Meanwhile, respondents stated that there was a large increase in family food needs with a percentage of 25% and 5% of respondents stated that there was a very large increase in family food needs during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Data on respondents' perceptions of food reserves for families during the early days of the Covid-19 pandemic can be seen in Figure 5. below.

Figure 7. Availability of Food Reserve

Based on Figure 7. above, 50% of respondents stated that there was sufficient family food supply during the Covid-19 pandemic and 30% of respondents stated that they did not have food reserves. The rest, respondents had a small amount of family food reserves during the Covid-19 pandemic with a percentage of 20%. Resilience is one of the main pillars in KpT. The formula used to collect data on families that need to be subsidized during a disaster is as in equation (1) below.

$$\begin{matrix} \text{Number} & \text{of} \\ \text{households} & \% \text{ of poor people in one city / district} \\ \text{Receiver} & = + 2\% - 3\% \text{ error} + 5\% - 10\% \text{ reserve} \\ \text{Assistance} & \text{(5 for rural and 10 for city)} \\ \text{(KPB)} & \end{matrix}$$

Note: This formula is verified between the actual data collection for the 0833 Kodim Malang City compared to the Covid19 formula for Universitas Brawijaya with an error of 3.6%.

Based on the equation (1) above, if the number of poor people is 10%, the foodstuffs that must be prepared by the government is $10\% + 3\% + 5\% = 18\%$ of the total population. This formula applies when the Covid-19 pandemic enters its second month, assuming that people who previously worked still have food reserves for at least the next 2 months.

In the following Figure 6., the percentage of respondents at 65% acknowledges that the urgency of food resilience is very necessary as an effort in overcoming the non-natural national disaster Covid-19. Meanwhile, 35% of respondents stated the need for food resilience as an effort to overcome the non-natural national disaster of Covid-19. Data on respondents' perceptions of the urgency of Food Resilience in the KpT social movement as a response to the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 6 as follows.

Figure 8. Availability of Food Reserves

Health Resilience

The installation of health resilience begins with upgrading health potentials such as village midwives, family planning cadres, and posyandu cadres. Village midwives, posyandu cadres or family planning or health cadres can have their skills added in dealing with the Covid-19 problem or recruiting new cadres if they are not there yet. The response to Covid-19 in health resilience includes the activities of corpses and funeral officers, because the bodies of Covid-19 patients require special treatment. Several KpTs in the Greater Malang area can independently complete the needs of health protocols, such as thermos, masks, hand washing stations and quarantine houses..

Data on respondents' perceptions of the efforts of resilient health families to family members during Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 7. as follows.

Figure 9. Efforts for Healthy Resilient Families

In Figure 9. above, respondents with a percentage of 65% stated that they made very many strong health efforts for family members. The rest, 20% of respondents stated that they did not make strong health efforts, 10% of respondents said they did not make strong health efforts and 5% respondents said they did not make strong health efforts for family members. According to the Indopol survey (2020), the government's performance in dealing with Covid-19 that is felt by the public is in the form of an appeal to comply with health protocols (62.2%), distribution of masks (16.1%), spraying disinfectants (9.7%), PSBB (4.9%), and distribution of hand sanitizers (0.3%) [26].

Based on the following Figure 8., 60% of respondents stated that they really need strong health cadres in handling people affected by Covid-19. Meanwhile, 40% of respondents said they needed a health cadre to handle residents affected by Covid-19 in rural areas. Data on respondents' perceptions of the need for resilient health cadres in handling people affected by Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 8 as follows.

Figure 10. Availability of Food Reserves

Data on respondents' perceptions of the urgency of resilient villages are needed in an effort to implement health protocols as an effort to prevent the spread of Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 9 below..

Figure 11. The role of resilient villages in implementing the recommended health protocols

In Figure 11. above, 70% of respondents admit that they really need the KpT social movement as a driving force for health protocols in the community. Meanwhile, 30% of respondents stated that a strong village social movement was needed to implement health protocols as an effort to prevent the spread of Covid-19.

Order and Security Resilience

Apartment / housing security guards, Citizens Association police or village security units, patrol officers and other elements of security and order (Kamtib) officers can work together to support strong security and order. Installing security and order's resilience requires adequate human resources, so that the National Police can quickly form a Village Security Unit (UPK) as part of installing security and order's resilience. UPK focuses on efforts to reduce the rate of spread of Covid-19 through "human control" by conducting screening, checking goods, restricting the movement of residents in an area, and so on..

Data on respondents' perceptions of increasing awareness of security and order at the family level during Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 10. below.

Figure 12. Efforts to increase community security and order

In Figure 11. above, respondents with a percentage of 75% stated that there were many efforts to increase awareness of order and security at the family level during the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, respondents with a percentage of respondents of 10% each stated that there was very much and little effort to increase awareness of security and order at the family level during the Covid-19 pandemic. The rest, respondents with a percentage of 5% stated that there was no effort to increase awareness of safety at the family level during the Covid-19 pandemic..

Based on Figure 11. below, 80% of respondents stated that they really need the presence of security officers (Bhayangkara Fostering Public Security and Order, Village Guidance Officer, and UPK) in maintaining security in their neighborhoods during the Covid-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, 20% of respondents stated that they needed the presence of security officers to maintain security at the village level during the Covid-19 pandemic. Data on the percentage of respondents' perceptions of the urgency of security and order officers at the village level during Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 13. The urgency of community security and order

Data on respondents' perceptions of the effort to Resilience Security in the social movement of Resilient Village as a response to the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 is presented in Figure 12 as follows.

Figure 14. The resilient urgency of security and order

In Figure 14., 75% of respondents admit that they really need strong security and order efforts in the KpT social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, 25% of respondents stated that the need for strong security and order efforts to the KpT social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic occurred. At the data collection stage, organizing and implementing security officers together with other village / sub-district pillars work together.

Information Resilience

Information resilience is the main resilience that needs to be built in the KpT social movement as an effort to overcome the non-natural national disaster of Covid-19. The fast flow of information circulating in the community can cause chaos if the truth and appropriateness of the information is not filtered. Apart from fighting hoaxes, strong information will give the public a sense of trust in the government so that all forms of programs will be supported by the community. Data on respondents' perceptions of increasing awareness of the increased need for information for families during Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 13. below.

Figure 15. Increasing of information needs

In Figure 15. above, respondents with a percentage of 65% stated that there was a large increase in the need for information related to prevention and handling of the impact of Covid-19. Furthermore, respondents with a respondent percentage of 20% stated that there was a slight increase in the need for information on the handling and prevention of Covid-19. The rest, respondents with a percentage of 10% stated that there was no increase in information needs and respondents with a percentage of 5% stated that there was a very large increase in the need for information on prevention and handling of the impact of Covid-19.

One example of information management to build information resilience is by providing media announcements to citizens. Although simple, notice boards can inform the types of assistance and methods of distribution, so that people understand and can avoid social conflicts. The notice board makes it easy for

Neighborhood Association or Citizens Association to socialize the form of assistance that will be provided to residents. Data on respondents' perceptions of the delivery of information on the prevention and handling of Covid-19 are as in Figure 14 below.

Figure 16. Methods of delivering information

Based on Figure 16. above, 60% of respondents stated that fairly effective information delivery was carried out for the prevention and handling of Covid-19. Meanwhile, respondents with a percentage of 25% stated that the method of delivering information was very effective regarding the prevention and handling of Covid-19. The rest, respondents, amounting to 15% of the method of delivering information, were normal in preventing and handling Covid-19. The method of conveying information in resilient villages is done with simple tools such as HT, TOA and bell notification.

Data on respondents' perceptions of Information Resilience efforts in the social movement of Resilient Village as a response to the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 15 as follows.

Figure 17. Delivery of information

In Figure 17. above, 60% of respondents admitted that they needed resilient information efforts in the KpT social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, 40% of respondents stated that a formidable information effort was needed on the KpT social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. Strengthening the system in conveying information is greatly strengthened in the KpT social movement so that it can reduce hoaxes and potential chaos / social conflict.

F. Psychological Resilience

Psychological resilience for the community is very important, because uncertainty and the end time for the Covid-19 pandemic cannot be ascertained. The ability to be resilient against mental stress is needed, in addition to the ability to physically endure such as food shortages and layoffs. Like plants, psychological resilience must be nurtured in various ways, such as ensuring food availability in the LPK, assistance from neighbors in case of shortages and entertainment by resilient information cadres. The resilient village consists of 7 resilience elements that support each other to become a defense system during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Data on respondents' perceptions of increasing attention to the psychological condition of family members during Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 16. as follows.

Figure 18. Improvement of family psychology

In Figure 18. above, respondents with a percentage of 65% stated that there was a lot of increased attention to the psychology of family members during the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, respondents with a respondent percentage of 20% stated that there was a slight increase in attention to the psychology of members of the needs and the remaining respondents with a percentage of 15% stated that there was no increase in attention to the psychological condition of family members during the Covid-19 pandemic. According to the RD respondent in Kalisongo Village, he has implemented strong psychological efforts with the presence of a village vent corner through media zoom, WA video call and google meet.

Data on respondents' perceptions of the needs of psychology cadres are needed in maintaining the psychological condition of the community at the village level can be seen in Figure 17 as follows.

Figure 19. The needs of psychology cadres

Based on Figure 19. above, 60% of respondents stated the need for psychological cadres in maintaining the psychological condition of the community. Meanwhile, respondents with a percentage of 40% stated that psychology cadres are urgently needed to maintain the psychological condition of the community during the Covid-19 pandemic. Psychological resilience efforts that can be done are creating entertainment programs according to local potential, such as entertainment made by residents of Cempluk village in Kalisongo Village.

Data on respondents' perceptions of efforts for psychological resilience in the resilient village social movement as a response to the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 18 as follows.

Figure 20. The Urgency of Psychological Resilience

In Figure 20. above, the percentage of respondents at 55% acknowledged the need for strong psychological efforts in the resilient village social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, 44% of respondents stated that strong psychological efforts were needed in a resilient village social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. The main purpose of psychological resilience is to prevent residents from mental stress due to the prolonged Covid-19 pandemic and reduce the potential for social disruption whose scope is increasingly widening in all sectors of life.

Culture Resilience

Researchers examined four cultures that grew and developed as a culture resilience effort from resilient Village, namely:

1. Culture of 'various'
2. Culture of 'reminding others'
3. Culture of 'helping'
4. Culture of 'tolerance'.

Data on respondents' perceptions of the increase in the 'culture of sharing' during the Covid-19 pandemic are as presented in Figure 19.

Figure 21. Increasing a 'sharing culture'

In Figure 21. above, respondents with a percentage of 65% stated that there was an increase in the 'culture of sharing' in efforts to prevent and deal with the impact of Covid-19 in their homes. Furthermore, respondents with a percentage of 15% stated that there was a slight increase in the culture of 'sharing' as an effort to prevent and deal with the impact of Covid-19 and the remaining respondents with a percentage of 10% each stated that there was little and no increase in the culture of 'sharing' in prevention efforts, and handling the impact of Covid-19 where he lived during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Based on the following Figure 20., 65% of respondents stated that there was a lot of improvement in the culture of 'reminding others' in efforts to prevent and manage the impact of Covid-19. Furthermore, respondents with a percentage of 25% stated that there was a slight increase in the culture of 'reminding others' and respondents with a percentage of 5% each stated that it was very much and there was no increase in the culture of 'reminding others' as an effort to prevent and deal with the impact of Covid-19 in residential village level. Data on respondents' perceptions of the increase in the culture of 'reminding others' during the Covid-19 pandemic can be seen in Figure 20.

Figure 22. Increased culture of 'reminding others'

In Figure 22 below, 80% of respondents acknowledged an increase in the culture of 'helping' as an effort to prevent and deal with the impact of Covid-19 in their village environment. Meanwhile, 10% of respondents stated that there was a slight increase in the culture of 'helping' as an effort to prevent and deal with the impact of Covid-19, handling affected by Covid-19.

Data on respondents' perceptions of the increase in 'helping' culture during the Covid-19 pandemic can be seen in Figure 21 as follows.

Figure 23. Increased 'helping' culture

Based on Figure 23 below, 75% of respondents stated that there was a large increase in the culture of 'tolerance' as an effort to prevent and deal with being affected by Covid-19 in resilient villages. Meanwhile, respondents with a percentage of 15% stated a slight increase in the culture of 'tolerance' and respondents with a percentage of 5% said that there was very much and no increase in the culture of 'tolerance' as an effort to prevent and deal with the impact of Covid-19 in their village environment. Data on respondents' perceptions of an increase in the culture of 'tolerance' during the Covid-19 pandemic can be seen in Figure 24 as follows.

Figure 24. Increased culture of 'tolerance'

Data on respondents' perceptions of the urgency of Cultural Resilience in the social movement of Resilient Village as a response to the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 can be seen in Figure 24. as follows.

Figure 25. The Urgency of Resilience Culture

In Figure 25. above, the percentage of respondents of 55% acknowledged that they really need strong cultural efforts in the KpT social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, 45% of respondents stated that a strong cultural effort was needed in the KpT social movement during the Covid-19 pandemic. Artists were upgraded to maintain the psychological resilience of citizens. Local radio broadcasters or IT enthusiasts are encouraged to manage information resilience. Information resilience, psychology, culture and health are interconnected, because information cadres are also obliged to design entertainment for local residents through the channels they have..

Conclusion

Based on the description of the resilience of rural communities as an effort to tackle the Covid-19 pandemic, some conclusions can be presented as follows:

1. Human resource resilience is measured by the level of confidence in the existence of Covid-19, willingness as a disaster management cadre and the urgency of a resilient village.
 - Respondents' belief in the occurrence of the non-natural national disaster Covid-19 shows that 95% are very confident, and 5% of respondents are not sure.

- The willingness of respondents as disaster management cadres stated that 85% were willing without conditions and 15% were willing with conditions.
 - Respondents stated that the urgency of a resilient village was 75% very necessary and 25% needed.
2. Food Resilience is assessed based on the increase in food demand, food availability and food resilience urgency.
 - The increase in food needs of respondents indicated a slight increase in 50%, 25% of respondents had a lot of increase, 20% of respondents did not increase, and 5% of respondents there was a very large increase in food needs.
 - The availability of food reserves of the respondents in the amount of 50% is sufficient food reserves, 30% respondents do not have food reserves and 20% respondents have little food reserves.
 - The urgency of food resilience shows that 65% of respondents really need it and 35% of respondents need food resilience.
 3. Health Resilience is researched based on the efforts of healthy resilient families, resilient health cadres and the urgency of healthy health.
 - Respondents' efforts of healthy resilient families showed 65% of the amount of effort, 20% of respondents had little effort, 10% of respondents had no effort and 5% of respondents showed very many efforts to create healthy resilient families.
 - Perception of health resilient cadres by respondents stated that 60% is very necessary and 40% respondents need health resilience cadres.
 - The urgency of the health resilience shows that 70% of respondents really need it and 30% of the respondents need the health resilience.
 4. Security and order resilience is examined on the improvement of security and order, the role of security and order officers, and the need for strong security and order.
 - Increased security and order by 75% of respondents, there was a lot of improvement, 10% of respondents each was very much an increase and a slight increase and 5% respondents did not have an increase in security and order.
 - Respondents acknowledged the role of security and order cadres by 80% of the respondents was very necessary and 20% respondents needed security and order cadres.
 - The strong urgency of security and order shows that 75% of respondents really need it and 25% of respondents need strong security and order.
 5. Information resilience is reviewed based on the increased need for information, information delivery and the need for robust information during the Covid-19 pandemic..
 - The increase in the need for information was acknowledged by 65% respondents that there was a lot of increase, 20% of respondents had a slight increase, 10% of respondents did not have an increase, and 5% respondents had an increase in information needs.
 - The method of conveying information according to 60% of respondents is quite effective, 25% of respondents are very effective and 15% of respondents stated that the method of conveying information is normal.
 - Strong information urgency shows that 60% of respondents need information and 40% of respondents really need strong information.
 6. Psychological resilience is researched according to the improvement of family psychology, the need for psychological cadres and the need for psychological strength.
 - The improvement in family psychology was acknowledged by 65% respondents that there was a lot of increase, 20% respondents had a slight increase and 15% respondents did not have an increase in family psychology.
 - The need for psychological cadres according to respondents was 60% needed and 40% respondents really needed psychology cadres during the Covid-19 pandemic.
 - The urgency of strong psychology shows that 55% of respondents need psychological strength and some 45% of respondents really need a strong psychology.
 7. Cultural resilience is studied based on a culture of sharing, a culture of reminding others, a culture of helping, a culture of tolerance and the need for cultural resilience.
 - The culture of sharing acknowledged by respondents that 65% is very common, respondents 15% are less common, respondents in 10% respectively occur very much and do not occur.
 - Culture reminds that according to respondents 65% is a lot happening, 25% respondent is small, 5% respondent each is very common and does not occur.
 - A culture of helping was felt by 80% of the respondents, it was a lot, 10% of respondents were very small, 5% of respondents each was very much and did not.
 - Culture of tolerance showed that 75% of respondents were prevalent, 15% of respondents were small, 5% respondents respectively were very numerous and did not occur.

- The urgency of cultural resilience shows that 55% of respondents really need it and some 45% of respondents need a strong culture.

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